

Vehicle accident detection and tracking using IoT

T. ANWESHA, T. RANJITHA DEVI, S. BINDU

ASSISTANT PROFESSOR ^{1,2,3}

anweshat9f@gmail.com, ranjitha.svitece@gmail.com, somaguttabindu94@gmail.com

Department of ECE, Sri Venkateswara Institute of Technology,

N.H 44, Hampapuram, Rapthadu, Anantapuramu, Andhra Pradesh 515722

Abstract—

Many of our once labor-intensive daily jobs have become much easier because to transportation advancements. Some people are talking about a new IoT gadget that uses GPS and WIFI to detect vehicle accidents. After an accident has occurred, this technology will be able to contact a phone number using WhatsApp over Wi-Fi. You will get the coordinates in two formats: long and short. With this information, we can pinpoint the exact location of the occurrence. Keywords- Internet connectivity, GPS, vibration sensor, L293D motor driver, Python, and a Raspberry Pi.

I INTRODUCTION

The linking of individually identifiable embedded computer devices inside the current Internet infrastructure is known as the Internet of Things (IoT). Beyond machine-to-machine communications (M2M), the Internet of Things (IoT) often provides improved connection of systems, devices, and services across a wide range of protocols, domains, and applications. Embedded electronics, which include smart items, are interconnected in almost every area of automation, allowing for sophisticated applications such as a Smart Grid. Electric clams in coastal waters, heart monitoring implants, field operation devices that aid firefighters in search and rescue, and autos with built-in sensors are just a few examples of the many gadgets that make up the word "things" in the context of the Internet of Things (IoT). Thermostat systems

and Wi-Fi-enabled washers and dryers are two current market examples. "Vehicle accident detection and tracking using IoT" is the title of our project. For this project, we're use Raspberry Pi. The system's LED will turn on when turned on, signalling that power is being delivered to the circuit. When our project's vibration sensors detect an obstruction, they will transmit an interrupt signal to the Raspberry Pi. When an accident occurs, the GPS system takes the coordinates of the offending car and relays them. A cellphone number will get this information over WhatsApp. Any device connected to the internet in the circuit will be able to receive this message. The values of longitude and latitude will be included in the message. It is possible to approximate the vehicle's location using these data. During transmission, the modem modulates the signal, and during reception, it demodulates it.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Many researchers carried out their studies on accident detection system. Aishwarya S.Rexpained an IoT based vehicle accident prevention and tracking system for night drivers .In this paper provides Eye Blink Monitoring System (EBM) that alerts the subject during state of drowsiness.[1] Sadhana B have explained Smart helmetintelligent safety for motorcyclist using raspberry pi and

open CV. The idea is obtained after knowing that there is increased number of fatal road accidents over the years. This project is designed to introduce safety systems for the motorcyclist to wear the helmet properly.[2] Sarika R. Gujar explained advanced Embedded System of Vehicle Accident Detection and Tracking System. The main objective of this system is to first detect the accident location and call for the emergency services. Vehicle accident detection is possible with the help of sensors. A GPS and GSM module helps to trace the vehicle. [3] Shailesh Bhavthankar explained Wireless System for Vehicle Accident Detection and Reporting using Accelerometer and GPS. In this paper, Accelerometer sensor is used to detect crash and GPS give location of vehicle. In case of any accident, the system send automated message to the preprogrammed number such as family member or emergency medical services via GSM. [4] Jagdish A.Patel explained Raspberry Pi based smart home. This paper aims at designing a basic home automation application on Raspberry Pi through Interfacing camera as security purpose and the algorithm for the same is

implemented in developed in python environment which is the default programming environment provided by Raspberry Pi.

III BLOCK DIAGRAM

The block diagram of the proposed system consists of the following components: Raspberry Pi, vibration sensor, GPS Modem, L293D motor drive, led, buzzer, power supply (12v DC). The above components are integrated as per the block diagram.

A. The raspberry pi A single-board computer the size of a credit card is called a Raspberry Pi. Originally equipped with 256 megabytes of RAM, subsequently updated (Model B & Model B+) to 512 MB, the Broadcom BCM2835 system on chip (SoC) houses the ARM1176JZFS 700 MHz CPU, the Video Core IV GPU, and the Raspberry Pi. The second-generation Raspberry Pi 2 (Model B) has twice as much random access memory (RAM) as its predecessor (the B+) and is six times faster overall.

Section B: The Vibration Sensor The choice of sensors and their placement on a machine continue to be crucial aspects in deciding the effectiveness of any monitoring programme, regardless of the advancements in vibration analysis and monitoring technology. Installing cheap sensors in the hopes of saving money is a poor investment since the data they produce is typically inaccurate and unreliable about the equipment in question.

C. Driver for L293D Motors This is based on the idea of an H-bridge. A bidirectional voltage-transfer H-bridge circuit is a two-way electrical connector. Because of the necessity to reverse the direction of voltage in order to turn a DC motor clockwise or anticlockwise, H-bridge ICs are perfect for this task.

D. The Global Positioning System (GPS) Device The GPS is a GNSS that is based in space and delivers accurate position and time information 24/7/365. Receivers on Earth are able to determine their location with the help of the GPS satellites, which serve as a reference point. Measuring pseudo-ranges between the user and four satellites is the basis of the navigation concept.

B. .

IV. HARDWARE IMPLEMENTATION

We are use a Raspberry Pi 3 for this project. The system's power indicator light (LED) will turn on when turned on to show that electricity is flowing to the circuit. The vibration sensor will notify the Raspberry Pi via interrupt whenever it detects an obstruction. When an accident occurs, the GPS system takes the coordinates of the offending car and relays them. An individual's phone will get this data via WhatsApp. Those on the circuit will be able to get this message thanks to the internet. You will get the values of longitude and latitude in this mail. It is possible to approximate the vehicle's location using these data. The Raspberry Pi receives the data. In a similar vein, it notifies the phone via WhatsApp that it has received the message. One of the circuit's LEDs shows the status of incoming messages. The devices are triggered via select lines internally incorporated into the internet, and the Raspberry Pi is interfaced to the GPS modem over the internet. The Raspberry Pi is connected to the internet using the transmit and receive pins. The Raspberry Pi may be connected to any available port by an LED, which shows the current state of the GPS modem and whether data is being read from it.

the python program to interface the raspberry pi. Python is widely used high-level programming language for general purpose programming

V. ADVANTAGES

- We can monitor the speed of the vehicle.
- We can find the location of the vehicle.
- Alert message to mobile phone for remote information.
- Mobile number can be changed at any time.

VI. LIMITATIONS: ➤ Costlier.

- Sending data not secure.
- This system is not applicable for poor network connection places.

VI. APPLICATIONS:

Vehicles used for transportation and automobiles.

Logistics, transportation, and remote monitoring are all part of security.

Another option is to connect this device to a car warning system.

VII. CONCLUSION:

The suggested system employs the Internet of Things (IoT) to identify and notify authorities of car accidents, as well as to monitor vehicles using GPS modems. We have developed an Internet of Things (IoT) system that uses GPS modems to identify and monitor car accidents in this project. Therefore, the Internet of Things has the potential to completely alter the manner in which systems interact and react across a wide range of applications, including traffic management.

VIII. FUTURE SCOPE:

This device may be connected to the airbag system in your car so that you and your passengers never have to worry about banging your head on the window or steering wheel. By connecting a camera to the controller, this may also be created. apparatus that records the accident site for the purpose of easy tracking via photography.

REFERENCES

[1] "An Internet of Things based vehicle accident prevention and tracking system for night drivers" (Proc. IEEE, vol.3, no.4, pp.2320-9798 2015), Aishwarya S.R., Ashish Rai, Charitha, Prasanth M.A., and Savitha S.C. "Smart helmet—intelligent safety for motorcyclist using raspberry pi and open CV," submitted by Sadhana B. Shabrin, Bhagyashree Jagadish Nikharge, Maithri M. Poojary, and T. Pooja to the Proceedings of the IEEE, volume 3, issue 3, pages 2395–0056. 2016 was the third "Raspberry Pi based smart home," Proc. IEEE, vol.6, no.3, pp.2321-3361 2016, was discussed by Jagdish A. Patel, Aringale Shubhangi, Shweta Joshi, Aarti Pawar, and Namrata Bari. [4] In their 2016 paper "An Efficient Management System based on Face Recognition using Matlab and Raspberry Pi 2," Drs. Pankaj Tomar and Preeti Mehta concentrate on this topic. The paper was published in the Proceedings of the 2016 IEEE Conference on Electrical Engineering.

"Android based home automation using Raspberry pi" was the topic of T. Anitha and T. Uppalaigh's 2016 paper in the Proceedings of the IEEE (vol.04, no.01, pp-2351-8665).

The paper "Wireless System for Vehicle Accident Detection and Reporting using Accelerometer and GPS" was addressed by Shailesh Bhavthankar and Prof. H.G. Sayyed in the Proceedings of the IEEE, volume 6, issue 8, pages 2229–5518. 2015 was "A Wireless Health Monitoring System Using Mobile Phone Accessories" was the main topic of the work of Md. Shaad Mahmud, Honggang Wang, A.M. Esfar-EAlam, and Hua Fang, as published in the Proceedings of the IEEE, volume 1, issue 99, pages 2327–4662. 2016 was "Advanced Embedded System of Vehicle Accident Detection and Tracking System," published in Proc-IEEE, volume 5, issue 2, pages 2277–1289X, was the subject of research by Sarika R. Gujar and Professor A. R. Itkikar. 2015 was [9] In their 2017 paper "Cost-Efficient Strategies for Restraining Rumour Spreading in Mobile Social Networks," Zaobo He, Zhipeng Cai, Jiguo Yu, Xiaoming Wang, Yunchuan Sun, and Yingshu Li reviewed the literature.

"Load Balancing Under Heavy Traffic in RPL Routing Protocol for Low Power and Lossy Networks," published in 2017 by the IEEE, was discussed by Hyung-Sin Kim, Hongchan Kim, Jeongyeuo Paek, and Saewoong Bahk.